

English learning perceptions and career implications: insights from tertiary-level students

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates students' perceptions of English language learning at the tertiary level, focusing on its importance for academic success and future career opportunities. The problem addressed is the gap in understanding how students perceive the relevance of English proficiency to their professional futures and the challenges they face in achieving proficiency. A descriptive-analytical and correlational research design was employed, using data from 127 students across various majors and years of study at the University of Jordan, with 122 valid responses. The research utilized a structured questionnaire to explore students' learning goals, perceived importance of English proficiency, and the challenges they face in language classes. Statistical analysis was applied to identify significant relationships between variables. The major findings reveal that students view English proficiency, particularly in speaking, as critical for their professional futures. However, challenges such as inadequate classroom resources and limited opportunities for practice were commonly reported. The proposed solution emphasizes the need for enhanced language instruction that aligns with students' professional goals, alongside improvements in classroom infrastructure and more practical language engagement opportunities. The study concludes that addressing these challenges could significantly improve students' English learning outcomes and better prepare them for their future careers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English has become the dominant language in fields such as science, business, and education. Proficiency in English is widely recognized as essential for professional success, particularly in non-English-speaking countries where it serves as a pathway to global opportunities. In Jordan, English is a mandatory subject in schools and universities and is considered vital for students' academic and career advancement. As demand for English skills continues to rise worldwide, higher education institutions are tasked with ensuring that graduates are equipped to compete in the international job market [1]. However, students in Jordan face challenges in attaining proficiency due to outdated teaching methods and limited exposure to practical language use [2], [3], which ultimately hinders their development and limits their career readiness. These barriers are further compounded by insufficient opportunities for real-world language practice and limited access to authentic English-speaking environments [4]. Research on students' perceptions of these challenges at the tertiary level remains limited, although understanding these

perspectives is essential to designing effective, targeted interventions [5]. This study aims to address this gap by examining students' perceptions of English language learning in Jordan, focusing on its relevance to their academic success and professional futures. By analyzing how demographic factors—such as major, year of study, and learning goals—influence students' views on English proficiency [6], and identifying specific challenges, this research offers actionable insights for improving English language education in Jordan. The study's findings are intended to guide the development of targeted educational strategies that align language instruction with professional needs, enhancing students' language skills and preparing them for their careers [7].

2. RESEARCH QUESTION

This study seeks to explore the perceptions of English language learning among students at the University of Jordan. The focus of the study is particularly in relation to the students' perceived importance of English learning for their future careers. The research is guided by several key questions that aim to uncover both the general and specific aspects of students' attitudes towards English language proficiency.

2.1. What is the level of perceptions of the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan?

Understanding students' perceptions of the importance of English is crucial, as it directly influences their motivation and engagement in language learning. As Alqarni *et al.* [8] posits, “the attitudes and perceptions of language learners are significant predictors of their success in acquiring a second language.” This research question aims to quantify the level of importance that students at the University of Jordan attach to English language learning in the context of their academic and professional aspirations.

2.2. What is the most important English skill for the student's future career from their own view?

Different English language skills—such as speaking, writing, reading, and listening—play varied roles in students' future careers, depending on their chosen fields. Previous study [9] have shown that “speaking and writing skills are often prioritized by students in business and technical fields, where communication is key.” This question investigates which specific language skills students believe are most critical for their professional success.

2.3. In their point of view, what are the main reasons or challenges those students are not doing well in the university's language classes?

Identifying the challenges faced by students in language classes is essential for improving English language education. Al-Issa [10] noted that “Arab learners of English often struggle with communication due to inadequate exposure and practice opportunities.” This question seeks to capture students' perspectives on the primary obstacles hindering their success in language classes, providing insights into potential areas for pedagogical improvement.

2.4. Is there a statistically significant relationship between the perceptions of the importance of learning English at tertiary level and professional future career among the students?

The correlation between students' perceptions of English and their professional goals is a critical area of investigation. This question aims to determine whether such a relationship exists among University of Jordan students or not. The results of such investigation could have implications for language education policies and practices.

2.5. Are there statistically significant differences in the level of perceptions of the importance of learning English at tertiary level due to student demographic data?

Demographic factors such as major, year of study, and gender may influence students' attitudes towards English learning. Research by Alostath [11] indicated that “students in scientific disciplines often exhibit higher motivation to learn English compared to those in the humanities.” This question examines whether similar patterns are evident at tertiary level, providing a nuanced understanding of how different student groups perceive the importance of English.

3. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

While this study provides valuable insights into the perceptions of English language learning among students at the University of Jordan, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the sample size of 127 students, while representative of various majors and years, is relatively small and may not fully capture the diversity of experiences and attitudes across the entire student body. Consequently, the findings may not

be generalizable to all students at the University of Jordan or other universities in the region. Second, the study relies on self-reported data obtained through surveys, which are inherently subject to biases such as social desirability bias, where respondents may provide answers, they believe are expected rather than their true opinions. This could potentially skew the results, particularly in questions related to perceived challenges and the importance of English in their future careers. Third, the cross-sectional design of the study limits its ability to establish causal relationships. While correlations between students' perceptions of English learning and their professional aspirations were explored, the study cannot definitively determine whether these perceptions directly influence their academic and career outcomes or are influenced by other unexamined factors. Additionally, the study's focus on the University of Jordan means that the findings may not be applicable to students in different educational contexts, particularly those in institutions with different language education policies, resources, or cultural attitudes toward English. The specific challenges and opportunities related to English learning at the University of Jordan may differ significantly from those in other universities, both within Jordan and internationally.

Finally, the study did not account for external factors such as students' access to English language resources outside the classroom, including private tutoring, online courses, or exposure to English through media and social interactions. Online platforms have been increasingly used to support English language learning, offering flexibility and accessibility that can enhance students' engagement and perception of the importance of language skills for their academic and professional futures [3]. These factors could play a significant role in shaping students' perceptions and proficiency but were beyond the scope of this research. Future studies could address these limitations by using larger, more diverse samples, employing longitudinal designs to track changes over time, and exploring the influence of external factors on students' English learning experiences. Despite these limitations, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how students at the University of Jordan perceive the role of English in their academic and professional lives, and it offers a foundation for further research in this area.

4. METHOD

The current study aims to investigate the perceptions of the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan and its relation to students' professional futures. This issue has gained increasing attention in education, particularly in non-English-speaking countries, as proficiency in English is often seen as a key factor for academic and career success [10]. To address this phenomenon, the researcher adopted a descriptive-analytical and correlational approach, which is well-suited to examining relationships between variables and providing an accurate description of the studied phenomenon [12].

4.1. Research design

This study employs a descriptive-analytical and correlational approach, which aligns with Sarı and Başkan [13] emphasis on the importance of flexibility in research design to accommodate the complexities of studying human perceptions and behaviors. This approach was chosen to accurately describe the students' perceptions of the importance of English learning and examine the relationship between these perceptions and their professional futures. The study also aimed to identify differences in these perceptions based on demographic variables such as major, year of study, and specific learning goals. This design aligns with existing literature, which emphasizes the need for a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing students' attitudes towards English learning in various educational contexts [9].

4.2. Primary and secondary sources

To build the questionnaire and theoretical framework, the study relied on both primary and secondary data sources. The primary data were collected using a questionnaire, which served as the main tool for gathering quantitative data from the study participants. This approach allowed for the collection of numerical data that reflected the opinions of the respondents and facilitated the analysis of their perceptions. According to Hitt *et al.* [14], "quantitative methods are essential for capturing the breadth of student perceptions in educational research."

In addition to the primary data, secondary sources were used to construct the theoretical framework. These included published research from international peer-reviewed journals, as well as books related to the theoretical literature on English language learning. The use of these sources ensured that the study was grounded in existing scholarship and allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the topic.

4.3. Data collection

The study employed a quantitative method to collect data from the participants through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed directly to 127 students, with 122 valid responses ultimately included in the analysis. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: the first focused on demographic

variables, including major, year of study, and specific goals for the English course. The second section addressed perceptions of the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan and its relevance to students' professional futures. The responses were analyzed based on frequencies, means, and standard deviations, providing a clear understanding of the students' views.

4.4. Study tool

The questionnaire was carefully designed to capture the key aspects of the study. It included 29 items divided into three dimensions: the importance of learning English (12 items), the most important English skills for future careers (7 items), and the main reasons or challenges students face in language classes (10 items). The validity of the study tool was ensured through expert review, and its internal consistency was confirmed using the Pearson correlation coefficient test. The correlation values for the statements ranged from .284 to .821, indicating acceptable levels of discrimination [15].

4.5. Validity and reliability

Researchers assessed the validity of the study tool to ensure that it accurately measured the intended constructs. Experts in language education reviewed the initial version of the questionnaire, and their feedback was used to refine the tool. This process resulted in the final version, consisting of 29 items as evident in Table 1. The internal construct validity was further confirmed using the Pearson correlation coefficient test, which showed that all statements had a significant relationship with their respective dimensions.

Table 1. The correlation coefficient of each statement with the dimension

The importance of English language		The most important English language skills for professional future		Challenges	
1	.660**	1	.695**	1	.637**
2	.669**	2	.769**	2	.673**
3	.653**	3	.821**	3	.619**
4	.648**	4	.804**	4	.617**
5	.700**	5	.767**	5	.749**
6	.625**	6	.696**	6	.711**
7	.634**	7	.669**	7	.594**
8	.430**			8	.671**
9	.493**			9	.696**
10	.462**			10	.639**
11	.284**				
12	.524**				

**The person correlation test showed that all statements have a relationship with their dimensions, values more than (.30), and significance at the level of (.01).

Reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, as shown in Table 2, which indicated satisfactory internal consistency across all dimensions of the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha values ranged from .789 to .864, exceeding the generally accepted threshold of .70 [16]. This suggests that the study tool consistently measured the perceptions of the study participants.

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for all the dimensions and total score of the scale

Variables	Statements	Cronbach alpha
The importance of English language	12-1	.789
The most important English language skills for professional future	7-1	.864
Challenges	10-1	.855

4.6. Data analysis techniques

To analyze the collected data, the study employed several statistical techniques using the SPSS software (version 22). The participants' responses were described using frequencies and percentages, while the internal construct validity of the study tool was confirmed through the Pearson correlation coefficient test. The reliability of the tool was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, which demonstrated consistent responses across the sample. To address the research questions, means and standard deviations were calculated, and a Three-Way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was conducted to examine differences in perceptions based on demographic variables. The study employed a seven-point Likert scale to measure participants' responses, with the results categorized into low, medium, and high degrees of agreement.

4.7. Participants

The study population consisted of students enrolled at the University of Jordan during the summer semester. To select participants for the study, a sample was determined using the “Thompson” sampling equation [17], with an error level of .05. This method resulted in a sample size of 127 students, who were chosen randomly. The researcher distributed questionnaires directly to these participants, ultimately excluding 5 questionnaires due to incomplete responses. The final study sample consisted of 122 participants, representing 96% of the initially chosen sample. The demographic characteristics of the participants are outlined in Table 3. The sample included students from both humanities and science majors, with 54.9% (n=67) of participants majoring in humanities and 45.1% (n=55) in science disciplines. In terms of their academic year, the participants were fairly distributed across all years of study: 18.0% (n=22) were freshmen, 19.7% (n=24) were sophomores, 23.0% (n=28) were juniors, and the largest group, 39.3% (n=48), were seniors.

Table 3. Demographical data for the participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Major		
Humanities majors	67	54.9
Science majors	55	45.1
Total	122	100.0
Year of study		
Freshman	22	18.0
Sophomore	24	19.7
Junior	28	23.0
Senior	48	39.3
Total	122	100.0
Specific goals for the English course		
Improve grammar	15	12.3
Enhance vocabulary	16	13.1
Improve speaking skills	48	39.3
Improve writing skills	12	9.8
Prepare for a specific test (e.g., TOEFL, IELTS)	4	3.3
Pass the course	24	19.7
I do not have any goals	3	2.5
Total	122	100.0

Additionally, the study examined the specific goals students had for their English courses. The majority of students, 39.3% (n=48), indicated that their primary goal was to improve their speaking skills, followed by 19.7% (n=24) who aimed to pass the course. Other goals included enhancing vocabulary (13.1%, n=16), improving grammar (12.3%, n=15), improving writing skills (9.8%, n=12), and preparing for specific tests such as TOEFL or IELTS (3.3%, n=4). A small percentage of participants, 2.5% (n=3), reported having no specific goals for the course.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current study aimed to explore students' perceptions of the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan. Moreover, it attempts to identify the most important English skills for their future careers from their own perspectives. It also examines the challenges they face in language classes, and investigates the relationships between these perceptions and their demographic data.

5.1. Perceptions of the importance of learning English

The findings from the analysis of the survey data indicate a high level of student perception regarding the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan. As shown in Table 4, the overall mean score for perceptions of English importance was 5.61, with a standard deviation of 1.30, indicating a high level of importance across the board. The highest-ranked item, “English proficiency is important for my future career” (mean=6.07), highlights students' belief that English will be indispensable in their professional lives. This mirrors findings from global studies that emphasize English as a critical skill in the job market where communication in English is essential as well as highlighting the interconnectedness of teacher and learner psychological factors [18].

Moreover, the perception that “proficiency in English will benefit my academic performance” (mean=6.04) also received a high score, suggesting that students see English as a tool for academic success. English for specific purposes (ESP) focuses on addressing learners' immediate and future professional needs,

enabling them to acquire language skills relevant to their careers [19]. The lowest-ranked item was the perception that the current English courses offered are sufficient to achieve professional-level proficiency (mean=4.51). This finding suggests that while students value English, they feel that existing courses do not fully meet their needs. Second language writing in the 21st century increasingly focuses on the connectedness of writing in multilingual contexts, highlighting the importance of addressing diverse linguistic needs [20].

Table 4. The level of perceptions of the importance of learning English at the University of Jordan in descending order

No	Perceptions	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Importance level
2	I think English proficiency for my future career is	6.07	1.30	1	High
6	I think proficiency in English will benefit my academic performance	6.04	1.39	2	High
1	I think learning English for my field of study is	5.99	1.33	3	High
5	I think I will use English in my future career	5.90	1.58	4	High
8	I think learning English will enhance my employment opportunities in Jordan	5.88	1.60	5	High
3	I think taking regular English courses after graduation is	5.84	1.52	6	High
7	I think this course will impact my future academic and professional goals	5.72	1.42	7	High
4	I use English in my current studies	5.50	1.92	8	High
12	It is mainly the teacher's responsibility to motivate students to learn English	5.39	1.75	9	High
10	I think the University of Jordan should offer more specified language courses	5.27	1.73	10	High
11	I think the University of Jordan should not force students to study English and to make it optional	5.19	1.95	11	High
9	I think the English courses offered as required courses at the University of Jordan are enough to learn English to a professional level	4.51	2.03	12	Medium
	Total	5.61			High

5.2. Most important English skills for future careers

When asked about the most important English skills for their careers, students prioritized “speaking” (mean=6.18) as the most critical skill, followed by “technical terminology” (mean=5.93) and “writing” (mean=5.88). The data in Table 5 reveal that “speaking” is the highest-ranked skill, with a mean score of 6.18. This finding is in line with the emphasis placed on oral communication skills in professional settings, where the ability to articulate ideas clearly and effectively is often a key determinant of success [21]. The global spread of English continues to shape professional and academic contexts worldwide, particularly in non-native English-speaking countries [22]. Effective language assessment, particularly of speaking skills, is crucial in measuring learners' proficiency and guiding instructional approaches [23].

Table 5. The level of most important English skills for the student's future career in descending order

No	Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Importance level
1	Speaking	6.18	1.38	1	High
5	Technical terminology	5.93	1.53	2	High
2	Writing	5.88	1.55	3	High
3	Reading	5.84	1.58	4	High
4	Listening	5.80	1.62	5	High
6	Understanding accents	5.72	1.52	6	High
7	Business English	5.32	1.91	7	High
	Total	5.81			High

The emphasis on speaking skills reflects the importance of oral communication in the workplace, particularly in roles that require presentations, negotiations, or teamwork in English [24]. Speaking skills are crucial for participating in meetings, negotiations, and presentations, which are common aspects of many professional roles. Astuty [24] analyzed the importance of oral communication skills in business education, highlighting their significance for professional communicative competence. The lower ranking of “business English” (mean=5.32) indicates that while students acknowledge the need for specialized English, they may not fully understand its relevance. This highlights a potential gap in the curriculum, where students may benefit from greater exposure to business communication skills as part of their language education [25].

5.3. Challenges in university language classes

The challenges identified by students in English language classes, as shown in Table 6, reflect broader systemic issues in language education. The top challenge was “classrooms are not properly equipped” (mean=5.30), followed closely by “no place to use the learned language outside of class”

(mean=5.29). Henry and Thorsen [26] examine how the ideal multilingual self and meaningful exposure to language environments foster motivation for second-language learners. The limited opportunities for using English outside of class hinder students' ability to practice the language, which is crucial for language acquisition. The need for adaptable language teaching methods that address the diverse linguistic backgrounds of students is critical. The role of English as a global language continues to shape multilingual education systems, where English is increasingly seen as essential for both academic achievement and professional success [27]. Additionally, Bacon and Finnemann [28] highlight that consistent and meaningful input plays a key role in achieving language proficiency. Moreover, inadequate resources can hinder the effectiveness of instruction and limit opportunities for practice [29]. Other significant challenges include a lack of confidence in using English (mean=5.26) and the lecture-based format of classes, which limits opportunities for active language practice (mean=5.01). Instructed language learning plays a critical role in guiding learners toward proficiency, with a focus on practical application and learner engagement [30].

Table 6. The main reason(s) that students are not doing well in the university's language classes (challenges) in descending order

No	Challenges	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Importance Level
1	The classrooms are not equipped properly	5.30	1.76	1	High
6	No place to use the learned language outside of class	5.29	1.82	2	High
8	Students do not have enough confidence to use the language in front of others	5.26	1.51	3	High
5	Classes are based on lectures and not enough practice	5.01	1.90	4	High
7	The class's atmosphere is uncomfortable	4.89	1.86	5	Medium
9	Students are careless and not doing the necessary work	4.82	1.56	6	Medium
4	Teaching methods are obsolete and outdated	4.57	1.91	7	Medium
10	Too much homework	4.57	1.64	7	Medium
2	The classroom surroundings are noisy	4.49	1.74	9	Medium
3	The class's time is not sufficient	3.82	1.85	10	Medium
	Total	4.80			Medium

5.4. Correlation between English learning and career success

There is a well-documented relationship between students' motivation levels and their overall language proficiency, with recent studies confirming that higher motivation correlates with improved outcomes in English as a foreign language (EFL) learners [5]. Understanding that English enables graduates to access a broader range of opportunities in the global workplace [31] enhances their learning abilities as well as motivation. The Pearson correlation analysis, as shown in Table 7, revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between students' perceptions of the importance of English and their professional future ($r=.665$, $p<.01$). This indicates that students who perceive English as important are more likely to believe it will play a significant role in their professional careers.

Research by Gan [6] explores the pivotal role of teacher-student relationships and engagement in enhancing student motivation and performance within EFL contexts. The positive correlation between motivation and language learning outcomes aligns with existing literature, which suggests that motivated students tend to engage more actively and perform better in language acquisition [32]. The strength of this correlation suggests that enhancing students' perceptions of English relevance could be a key strategy in motivating them to engage more fully with their language studies. This could involve more explicit connections between course content and professional applications, as well as the incorporation of career-oriented language activities.

Table 7. Pearson correlation test

The perceptions	Professional future career
Pearson correlation	.665**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
N	122

** : Significant at level of (.01).

5.5. Differences in perceptions based on demographic data

Finally, the three-way ANOVA analysis in Tables 8 and 9 did not show statistically significant differences in students' perceptions based on demographic variables such as major, year of study, or specific language learning goals. However, slight variations in mean scores suggest that while the overall perception

of English importance is high, different student groups may prioritize specific aspects of language learning. For example, students preparing for standardized tests (e.g., TOEFL, IELTS) showed a slightly lower perception of the overall importance of English learning, indicating that their focus may be more targeted toward test preparation rather than broader language acquisition.

Table 8. Mean and standard deviation

Source	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Major			
Humanities majors	67	5.58	.87
Science majors	55	5.64	.95
Study year			
Freshman	22	5.81	.92
Sophomore	24	5.57	.74
Junior	28	5.83	.63
Senior	48	5.40	1.06
Specific goals			
Improve grammar	15	5.71	.80
Enhance vocabulary	16	5.65	.78
Improve speaking skills	48	5.67	.83
Improve writing skills	12	5.92	.76
Prepare for a specific test (e.g., TOEFL, IELTS)	4	4.73	1.28
Pass the course	24	5.29	1.10
I do not have any goals	3	6.31	.49

Table 9. Three-way ANOVA test to show the statistically significant differences

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Major	.230	1	.230	.295	.588
Year	3.097	3	1.032	1.326	.270
Goals	7.334	6	1.222	1.570	.163
Error	86.441	111	.779		
Total	3934.118	122			
Corrected total	98.298	121			

6. INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study's findings provide valuable insights into tertiary-level students' perceptions of English language learning in Jordan, highlighting the language's perceived importance in their academic and professional futures. The analysis reveals that students overwhelmingly view English proficiency as essential, particularly in speaking skills, for career advancement. This aligns with global studies demonstrating English's role as a gateway to international career opportunities, particularly in non-English-speaking regions where English serves as a lingua franca in professional contexts [1]. Furthermore, the significant role of speaking skills echoes prior research, which identifies communicative competence as a critical aspect of career success in EFL contexts [6].

Despite the positive perceptions of English's importance, students face numerous challenges in attaining proficiency, primarily due to traditional teaching methods and limited practical exposure. These findings support existing literature that highlights similar challenges in EFL learning environments, where outdated pedagogical approaches and insufficient real-world language practice restrict language acquisition [2], [4]. The lack of practice and authentic English-speaking contexts not only hinders students' language development but also limits their ability to use English effectively in professional scenarios, suggesting a gap between current educational practices and real-world needs. Addressing this gap is crucial, as previous studies emphasize that students who engage in communicative language teaching and practical language use are better prepared for workplace demands [7].

The study's implications underscore the need for reform in English language education at the tertiary level. Aligning language instruction with students' career aspirations requires integrating more practical, communicative methods that focus on real-world application. This could involve collaborative activities, simulations, and industry partnerships that allow students to practice English in relevant contexts. Additionally, investment in classroom resources and opportunities for language exposure outside the classroom, such as internships or language exchanges, could greatly enhance students' engagement and proficiency levels. Enhancing instructional methods in these ways would not only improve language outcomes but also help students feel more prepared for professional success.

Future research should further explore how specific instructional approaches impact different aspects of language proficiency among students, as well as how students' perceptions evolve over time and across various fields of study. Examining how these factors interact with demographic variables—such as students' major or year of study—would also provide valuable insights for creating targeted educational policies. Ultimately, findings from such research could inform curriculum development, equipping educators to better meet the professional and academic needs of their students in an increasingly globalized world.

7. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the critical importance of English language proficiency for tertiary-level students in Jordan, particularly its role in shaping academic success and career readiness. The findings reveal that while students highly value English proficiency, especially in speaking skills, they face persistent challenges such as limited practice opportunities, poorly equipped classrooms, and a lack of confidence in using the language. These barriers indicate a misalignment between current language education practices and the demands of the global workforce.

The implications of this research suggest the need for curriculum reform to integrate career-oriented content and real-world applications, such as professional simulations and role-playing, to better align language instruction with students' aspirations. Additionally, investments in modern classroom infrastructure, including technological tools and language labs, can foster more interactive and communicative teaching methods. Addressing the lack of opportunities for practical language use outside the classroom through conversation clubs, internships, and partnerships with English-speaking organizations could significantly enhance students' fluency and confidence. Future research should explore the nuanced factors influencing students' attitudes toward English learning to develop tailored strategies that meet the diverse needs of learners. By addressing these challenges, educational institutions can enhance the effectiveness of their English programs and better prepare students for success in an increasingly globalized workforce.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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